

IMPORTANCE ,TYPES AND IMPACT OF MIS

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Abstract

MIS professionals help organizations to maximize the benefit from investments in personnel, equipment, and business processes. MIS is people-oriented, with an emphasis on service. Although today it is increasingly built on computer hardware, software and networks, it does not necessarily have to be computer-based. Management information systems are distinct from other information systems in that they are used to analyze and facilitate strategic and operational activities. Management Information Systems are designed to give managers the right information to make the right decision.

Key Word: Evolution, Advantages, Types, Applications

WHAT IS MIS:

Management Information Systems (MIS) is the studies of people, technology, organizations, and the relationships among them. This definition relates specifically to MIS as a course of study in business schools and refers to the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations evaluate, design, implement, manage, and utilize systems to generate information to improve efficiency and effectiveness of decision making, including systems termed decision support systems, expert systems, and executive information systems. Many business schools (or colleges of business administration within universities) have an MIS department, alongside departments of accounting, finance, management, marketing, and may award degrees (at undergraduate, master, and doctoral levels) in MIS. A definition of MIS in practice has been given in a journal article

IMPORTANCE OF THE MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM:

Management Information Systems (MIS) not only include software systems, but the entire set of business processes and resources that are used to pull together information from functional or tactical systems. Data is then presented in a user-friendly and timely manner so that mid and upper-level managers can use it to take the right actions. The entire system is designed so that the company will meet its strategic and tactical goals.

It goes without saying that all managerial functions are performed through decision-making; for taking rational decision, timely and reliable information is essential and is procured through a logical and well structured method of information collecting, processing and disseminating to decision makers. Such a method in the field of management is widely known as MIS. In today's world of ever increasing complexities of business as well as business organization, in order to service and grow , must have a properly planned, analyzed, designed and maintained MIS so that it provides timely, reliable and useful information to enable the management to take speedy and rational decisions.

MIS has assumed all the more important role in today's environment because a manager has to take decisions under two main challenges:

First, because of the liberalization and globalization, in which organizations are required to compete not locally but globally, a manager has to take quick decisions, otherwise his business will be taken away by his competitors. This has further enhanced the necessity for such a system.

Second, in this information age wherein information is doubling up every two or three years, a manager has to process a large voluminous data; failing which he may end up taking a strong decision that may prove to be very costly to the company.

In such a situation managers must be equipped with some tools or a system, which can assist them in their challenging role of decision-making. It is because of the above cited reasons, that today MIS is considered to be of permanent importance, sometimes regarded as the name centre of an organization. Such system assist decision makers in organizations by providing information

at various stages of decision making and thus greatly help the organizations to achieve their predetermined goals and objectives. On the other hand, the MIS which is not adequately planned for analyzed, designed, implemented or is poorly maintained may provide developed inaccurate, irrelevant or obsolete information which may prove fatal for the organization. In other words, organizations today just cannot survive and grow without properly planned, designed, implemented and maintained MIS. It has been well understood that MIS enables even small organizations to more than offset the economies of scale enjoyed by their bigger competitors and thus helps in providing a competitive edge over other organizations.

SIGNIFICANCE:

Organizations have multiple functional systems. These usually include sales systems, call center systems, financial systems, inventory systems, logistic systems and more. MIS combines information from multiple systems. This helps management staffers better understand their own departments' contributions. In many cases, the combination of data, such as sales figures combined with available inventory, help the manager take the appropriate action in order to meet the customer's needs.

FUNCTION:

The primary function of MIS is to help a manager take an action, answer a question or ask the right question. The questions or actions should directly relate to tactical or strategic goals. A sales manager who uses projections from the financial systems to compare with actual sales from the sales system can better gauge whether goals will be met. If the target is not going to be met, then the manager and his group can review their past actions and make necessary changes in order to increase sales and meet goals.

TYPES:

MIS is not necessarily a specific combination of functional systems, but instead is created based upon the business need. CRM (Customer Relationship Management) systems combine data that relates directly to the customer experience. ERP (Enterprise Resource Systems) combine data used in the entire sales process. Decision Support Systems or Data Warehouse often combine

summary data from multiple systems in order to show executives a snapshot view of the entire organization.

CONSIDERATIONS:

Prior to starting an MIS project, organizations need to carefully review the transactional systems, the business processes and the needs of management within an organization. As an MIS project grows, so does the cost of implementing a solution, managing the information processes and monitoring daily activities. The result of an MIS project must provide value back to the organization in order to be worth the cost.

MISCONCEPTIONS:

Many managers mistakenly believe that, for MIS to be effective, all data from all systems must be combined. The value of MIS is based upon how much it can help managers manage. If this means bringing just the data needed from several systems and ignoring the rest for now, the end result still has worth, which is the ultimate goal of MIS.

MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM EVOLUTION:

Kenneth and Jane Laudon identify five *eras* of Management Information System evolution corresponding to the five phases in the development of computing technology:

1. mainframe and minicomputer computing,
2. personal computers,
3. client/server networks,
4. enterprise computing, and
5. cloud computing.

The *first era* (mainframe and minicomputer) was ruled by IBM and their mainframe computers; these computers would often take up whole rooms and require teams to run them — IBM supplied the hardware and the software. As technology advanced, these computers were able to

handle greater capacities and therefore reduce their cost. Smaller, more affordable minicomputers allowed larger businesses to run their own computing centers in-house.

The *second era* (personal computer) began in 1965 as microprocessors started to compete with mainframes and minicomputers and accelerated the process of decentralizing computing power from large data centers to smaller offices. In the late 1970s minicomputer technology gave way to personal computers and relatively low cost computers were becoming mass market commodities, allowing businesses to provide their employees access to computing power that ten years before would have cost tens of thousands of dollars. This proliferation of computers created a ready market for interconnecting networks and the popularization of the Internet. (NOTE that the first microprocessor - a four-bit device intended for a programmable calculator - was introduced in 1971, and microprocessor-based systems were not readily available for several years. The MITS Altair 8800 was the first commonly-known microprocessor-based system, followed closely by the Apple I and II. It is arguable that the microprocessor-based system did not make significant inroads into minicomputer use until 1979, when VisiCalc prompted record sales of the Apple II on which it ran. The IBM PC introduced in 1981 was more broadly palatable to business, but its limitations gated its ability to challenge minicomputer systems until perhaps the late 1990- 1980s.)

TYPES AND TERMINOLOGY:

The terms *management information system* (MIS), *information system*, *enterprise resource planning* (ERP), and *information technology management* are often confused. Information systems and MIS are broader categories that include ERP. Information technology management concerns the operation and organization of information technology resources independent of their purpose.

- *Management information systems*, produce fixed, regularly scheduled reports based on data extracted and summarized from the firm's underlying transaction processing systems to middle and operational level managers to identify and inform structured and semi-structured decision problems.

- *Decision support systems (DSS)* are computer program applications used by middle and higher management to compile information from a wide range of sources to support problem solving and decision making. A DSS is used mostly for semi-structured and unstructured decision problems.
- *Executive information systems (EIS)* is a reporting tool that provides quick access to summarized reports coming from all company levels and departments such as accounting, human resources and operations.
- *Marketing Information Systems* are Management Information Systems designed specifically for managing the marketing aspects of the business.
- *Office automation systems (OAS)* support communication and productivity in the enterprise by automating workflow and eliminating bottlenecks. OAS may be implemented at any and all levels of management.
- *School Information management systems (SIMS)* cover school administration, and often including teaching and learning materials.
- *Enterprise resource planning* facilitates the flow of information between all business functions inside the boundaries of the organization and manage the connections to outside stakeholders.

ADVANTAGES:

The following are some of the benefits that can be attained using MISs.

- Companies are able to identify their strengths and weaknesses due to the presence of revenue reports, employees' performance record etc. Identifying these aspects can help a company improve its business processes and operations.
- Giving an overall picture of the company.
- Acting as a communication and planning tool.
- The availability of customer data and feedback can help the company to align its business processes according to the needs of its customers. The effective management of customer data can help the company to perform direct marketing and promotion activities.

- MISs can help a company gain a competitive advantage. Competitive advantage is a firm's ability to do something better, faster, cheaper, or uniquely, when compared with rival firms in the market.

ENTERPRISE APPLICATIONS:

- *Enterprise systems*—also known as *enterprise resource planning (ERP)* systems—provide integrated software modules and a unified database that personnel use to plan, manage, and control core business processes across multiple locations. Modules of ERP systems may include finance, accounting, marketing, human resources, production, inventory management, and distribution.
- *Supply chain management (SCM)* systems enable more efficient management of the supply chain by integrating the links in a supply chain. This may include suppliers, manufacturers, wholesalers, retailers, and final customers.
- *Customer relationship management (CRM)* systems help businesses manage relationships with potential and current customers and business partners across marketing, sales, and service.
- *Knowledge management system (KMS)* helps organizations facilitate the collection, recording, organization, retrieval, and dissemination of knowledge. This may include documents, accounting records, unrecorded procedures, practices, and skills. Knowledge management (KM) as a system covers the process of knowledge creation and acquisition from internal processes and the external world. The collected knowledge is incorporated in organizational policies and procedures, and then disseminated to the stakeholders.

DEVELOPMENT:

"The actions that are taken to create an information system that solves an organizational problem are called system development". These include system analysis, system design, computer programming/implementation, testing, conversion, production and finally maintenance.

Conversion is the process of changing or converting the old system into the new. This can be done in three basic ways, though newer methods (prototyping, Extreme Programming, JAD, etc.) are replacing these traditional conversion methods in many cases:

- Direct cut – The new system replaces the old at an appointed time.
- Pilot study – Introducing the new system to a small portion of the operation to see how it fares. If good then the new system expands to the rest of the company.

ROLE OF MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM:

The role of the MIS in an organization can be compared to the role of heart in the body. The information is the blood and MIS is the heart. In the body the heart plays the role of supplying pure blood to all the elements of the body including the brain. The heart work faster and supplies more blood when needed. It regulates and controls the incoming impure blood, processed it and sends it to the destination in the quantity needed. It fulfills the needs of blood supply to human body in normal course and also in crisis.

The MIS plays exactly the same role in the organization. The system ensures that an appropriate data is collected from the various sources, processed and send further to all the needy destinations. The system is expected to fulfill the information needs of an individual, a group of individuals, the management functionaries: the managers and top management.

Here are some of the important roles of the MIS:

- i. The MIS satisfies the diverse needs through variety of systems such as query system, analysis system, modeling system and decision support system.
- ii. The MIS helps in strategic planning, management control, operational control and transaction processing. The MIS helps in the clerical personal in the transaction processing and answers the queries on the data pertaining to the transaction, the status of a particular record and reference on a variety of documents.

iii. The MIS helps the junior management personnel by providing the operational data for planning, scheduling and control , and helps them further in decision-making at the operation level to correct an out of control situation.

iv. The MIS helps the middle management in short term planning, target setting and controlling the business functions. It is supported by the use of the management tools of planning and control.

v. The MIS helps the top level management in goal setting, strategic planning and evolving the business plans and their implementation.

FORMATION SYSTEM:

MIS plays a very important role in the organization; it creates an impact on the organization's functions, performance and productivity.

The impact of MIS on the functions is in its management with a good MIS supports the management of marketing, finance, production and personnel becomes more efficient. The tracking and monitoring of the functional targets becomes easy. The functional managers are informed about the progress, achievements and shortfalls in the activity and the targets. The manager is kept alert by providing certain information indicating and probable trends in the various aspects of business. This helps in forecasting and long-term perspective planning. The manager's attention is bought to a situation which is expected in nature, inducing him to take an action or a decision in the matter. Disciplined information reporting system creates structure database and a knowledge base for all the people in the organization. The information is available in such a form that it can be used straight away by blending and analysis, saving the manager's valuable time.

The MIS creates another impact in the organization which relates to the understanding of the business itself. The MIS begins with the definition of data, entity and its attributes. It uses a dictionary of data, entity and attributes, respectively, designed for information generation in the organization. Since all the information systems use the dictionary, there is common understanding of terms and terminology in the organization bringing clarity in the communication and a similar understanding of an event in the organization.

The MIS calls for a systematization of the business operations for an effective system design. This leads to streaming of the operations which complicates the system design. It improves the

administration of the business by bringing a discipline in its operations as everybody is required to follow and use systems and procedures. This process brings a high degree of professionalism in the business operations.

The goals and objectives of the MIS are the products of business goals and objectives. It helps indirectly to pull the entire organization in one direction towards the corporate goals and objectives by providing the relevant information to the organization.

A well designed system with a focus on the manager makes an impact on the managerial efficiency. The fund of information motivates an enlightened manager to use a variety of tools of the management. It helps him to resort to such exercises as experimentation and modeling. The use of computers enables him to use the tools and techniques which are impossible to use manually. The ready-made packages make this task simple. The impact is on the managerial ability to perform. It improves decision-making ability considerably high.

MIS is a vital part of IT

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